

Assessment on Use of Zoom Technology for Learning among Undergraduate Students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State.

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Abstract

This study investigated the use of Zoom Technology for learning among undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions guided the study. The population of the study consists of all undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria during the 2023/2024 academic session. A total number of three hundred and sixty (360) male and female students were randomly selected from target population. Undergraduate Students Use of Zoom Technology Questionnaire (USUZTQ) was used to collect data for the study. Data collected were analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation. The findings of the study revealed that: the level of use of zoom technology for learning among undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State was low; the perceived ease of use of zoom technology among undergraduate students was high. Also there were several challenges faced in using Zoom Technology for learning among undergraduates. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that the use of zoom technology should be encouraged among undergraduate students.

Keywords: Technology, Zoom, Use, Students, Learning, Undergraduate

Introduction

The evolvement of information and communication technology (ICT) into the tertiary education system has rapidly transformed education globally especially in teaching and learning process. In many countries of the world, the use of technology has shifted the learning pattern from traditional methods of instructions to online or e-learning modes especially in teacher education programme. Online instruction has become one of the current techniques in the learning activities of students through the use of internet tools that can be assessable on a computer or laptop, phones and other android devices. Guzacheva (2020) defines online learning as the acquisition of knowledge which takes place through electronic technologies and media. Palmer (2018) also describes online learning as a form of distance education in which a course or programmes is intentionally designed in advance to be delivered fully electronically. Similarly, Suardi (2020) avers that online instruction is a learning process that utilizes electronic tool for implementing learning process. Abidoye & Fakokunde (2015) asserted that, online learning has become the largest sector of distance learning in recent years which gives learners the opportunity to learn without their presence in the classroom.

Zoom is one of the different tools of technology used to carry out online learning. Eze & Chinadu (2018) describes zoom as a technology that enables representative real-time remote learning which an interactive audio and video program is based on Cloud technology. Suardi (2020) also refers zoom to an application that is operated via computer and android so that teachers and learners can make the learning process effective and efficient, easy to use anywhere and anytime. According to Lai & Bowa (2019), zoom combines video conferencing, online meetings and in-conference group, chat info is one easy-to-use tool that is ideal for online class, and group work.

The use of zoom technology has become increasingly popular globally for instructional delivery in recent years, and educators are discovering many benefits it offers. One of the most significant benefits of zoom technology in education is its ability to make teaching and learning process easier and gives the opportunity to teachers and learners to expand their knowledge better (Palmer 2018). Andriyani & Sari (2020).avers that zoom cloud meetings is a very useful alternative application for virtual meeting to facilitate communication with many people without making direct contact and be able to support learning needs in today's digital era. Adnan (2020) also claims that zoom meeting application is very helpful in

communicating remotely; all lecturers' explanations can be conveyed to the learners directly without having to meet physically. Zoom facilitate discussions between lecturers and students and among students with direct communication through video conference which is supported by zoom features such as raise hand and group messages, so that if there are problems in audio, the students are helped with the available chat features. Lai & Bowa (2019) explains that zoom combines video conferencing, online meetings and in-conference group, chat info is one easy-to-use tool that is ideal for online class, and group work. Zoom gives Breakout Rooms, which is not accessible in other video conferencing tools. This component empowers the teacher to separate the members into smaller class groups. This component is useful in delivering lecture and presentations. The teacher can look in on each class to examine the situation of introduction and the discussion among the members.

However, the use of zoom technology especially for instructional purposes is characterized with some notable challenges. Eze & Chinadu (2018) identified the following challenges confronting the use of zoom application, such challenges include lack of good network connection; power outages; lack of technological knowledge; high bundle consumption; and lack of devices for online learning such as smart mobile phones, computers, tablets, desktop, and smart televisions. Julius, et al (2021) also claimed that zoom app has limited capacity to accommodate more participants during the teaching and learning process. Adnan (2020) also avers that zoom is facing many security issues that pose a serious threat to its popularity. He said further that the secret IDs provided to join the meeting can be predicted effortlessly, permitting anybody to enter the meeting. However, the need to examine the extent of use of zoom technology in tertiary institutions especially Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo necessitated this research paper.

Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo is one of the teacher training universities recently created by the federal government of Nigeria located in Ondo in the south western part of the country. It was formally a college of education for years.

The use of zoom technology in tertiary institutions globally has been one of the key factors in ensuring effective teaching and learning. With the commencement of zoom technology in different sectors, universities inclusive, one would expect to see a holistic and integrated application and utilization of technologies and other platform of e-learning, of which Zoom technology is an exemplary part, in the provision and utilization of effective teaching and learning in universities. It has been observed that there has been relatively poor utilization of Zoom technology for teaching and learning especially among undergraduate students in Adeyemi Federal University of Education (AFUED) Ondo, Ondo State. Therefore, this study investigates the use of zoom technology for learning among undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The general purpose of this study is to assess the use of zoom technology for learning among undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examines:

1. The extent in which undergraduate students use zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State.
2. The level of ease in which undergraduate students experience while using zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State.
3. The challenges in which undergraduate students experience while using technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guide the study;

1. What is the mean response of the respondents on the extent to which undergraduate students use zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?
2. What is the mean response of the respondents on the level of ease while using zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?
3. What is the mean response of the respondents on the challenges while using zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions guided the study. The population of the study consists of all undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria during the 2023/2024 academic session. A total number of three hundred and sixty (360) male and female students

were randomly selected from target population. Undergraduate Students Use of Zoom Technology Questionnaire (USUZTQ) was used to collect data for the study. The instrument was divided into four sections A-D. Section A focuses on demographic information of respondents. Section B consisted of ten question items eliciting information on the assessment of level of use of zoom technology for learning by the undergraduate students. Section C focuses on the level of ease of use of zoom technology. While section D consisted of 10 question items sought information on the challenges of using zoom technology for learning. A 4-point Likert Scale response modes: Strongly Agree (SA = 4), Agree (A = 3), Disagree (D = 2) and Strongly Disagree (SD = 1) was used. Face and content validation of the instrument was carried out by an expert in test measurement and evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundation and Counselling Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti. Cronbach Alpha technique was used to determine the level of reliability of the instrument. The reliability coefficient of 0.73 was obtained and this was considered to be high enough to justify the use of the instrument. Data collected were analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the mean response of the respondents on the extent to which undergraduate students use zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?

Table 1 Level of Use of Zoom Technology by Undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D
I use zoom in sharing information in educational blogs via cloud meetings	45	41	87	187	1.84	1.05
I use Zoom cloud meetings to facilitate communication with many people	13	14	150	183	1.60	.73
I use zoom to read, view or listen to online academic programmes through my cell-phones and other Internet facilities	44	39	87	190	1.83	1.05
I use zoom to attempt online assignments with instructions and guides from learning platforms	42	57	92	169	1.92	1.04
I can still concentrate on learning through zoom meetings in online learning	259	81	20	0	3.66	.57
I use zoom technology to improve my interaction with others on my academic works	94	76	88	102	2.44	1.15
I use zoom technology to have access to learning anywhere and anytime	8	88	35	229	1.65	.92
I use zoom cloud meeting to share course materials with my classmates easy.	71	71	73	145	2.19	1.16
I use zoom meeting to get feedback on my academic work.	39	85	89	147	2.04	1.04
I use zoom to accomplish my academic tasks easily and quickly	32	95	51	182	1.94	1.06
Weighted Average						2.11

Key; SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree

Decision Value: Low = 0.00-2.44, High = 2.45-4.00

Table 1 shows the level of use of Zoom technology for learning among undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education (AFUED). The table shows that the respondents disagreed to the following items: they use zoom in sharing information in educational blogs via cloud meetings (\bar{x} = 1.84), use Zoom cloud meetings to facilitate communication with many people (\bar{x} = 1.60), use zoom to read, view or listen to online academic programmes through my cell-phones and other Internet facilities (\bar{x} = 1.83), use zoom to attempt online assignments with instructions and guides from learning platforms (\bar{x} = 1.92), use zoom technology to improve their interaction with others on their academic works (\bar{x} = 2.44), use zoom technology

to have access to learning anywhere and anytime ($\bar{x} = 1.65$), use zoom cloud meeting to share course materials with their classmates easy ($\bar{x} = 2.19$), use zoom meeting to get feedback on their academic work ($\bar{x} = 2.04$), and use zoom to accomplish their academic tasks easily and quickly ($\bar{x} = 1.94$). Also, the table shows that the undergraduates strongly agreed that: they are learning through internet simulated tutorials without a physical teacher ($\bar{x} = 3.66$). Meanwhile, based on the value of the weighted average (2.11 out of 4.00 maximum value obtainable) which falls, within the decision value for **low**, it can be inferred that the level of use of Zoom Technology for learning among undergraduate students in Adeyemi Federal University of Education (AFUED) is low.

Research Question 2:

What is the mean response of the respondents on the level of ease while using zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?

Table 2: Perceived Ease of Use of Zoom Technology for Teaching and Learning

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D	
I do not have confidence to use zoom technologies	45	90	122	103	2.21	0.99	
I belief that zoom technologies are too cumbersome for me to use	38	104	151	67	2.31	0.89	
I feel interaction with zoom technologies will be very beneficial	132	108	66	54	2.88	1.07	
I feel it is easy to use zoom technologies	103	97	96	64	2.66	1.07	
I believe I have the necessary skills to use zoom technologies	220	110	30	0	3.44	0.65	
It is easy to become skillful, if zoom technology is fully integrated	131	104	104	21	2.96	0.94	
The use of zoom for instruction would enable me cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease.	190	135	22	13	3.39	0.76	
Zoom web application is user friendly to me	109	184	50	17	3.07	0.79	
The flexibility of zoom technology would ensure speedy dissemination of information easily.	152	100	70	38	3.02	1.02	
Zoom technology makes my academic works easy and faster	117	101	104	38	2.83	1.00	
Weighted Average						2.88	

Key; *SD* = Strongly Disagree, *D* = Disagree, *A* = Agree, *SA* = Strongly Agree

Decision Value: *Low* = 0.00-2.44, *High* = 2.45-4.00

Table 2 shows the perceived ease of use of zoom technology for learning among undergraduates in AFUED. The table shows that the undergraduates disagreed that: they do not have confidence to use zoom technologies ($\bar{x} = 2.21$) and belief that zoom technologies are too cumbersome for me to use ($\bar{x} = 2.31$). Furthermore, the table also shows that the undergraduates agreed to the following: feel interaction with zoom technologies will be very beneficial ($\bar{x} = 2.88$), feel it is easy to use zoom technologies ($\bar{x} = 2.66$), believe they have the necessary skills to use zoom technologies ($\bar{x} = 3.44$), it is easy to become skillful, if zoom technology is fully integrated ($\bar{x} = 2.96$), the use of zoom for instruction would enable them cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease ($\bar{x} = 3.39$), Zoom web application is user friendly to them ($\bar{x} = 3.07$), the flexibility of zoom technology would ensure speedy dissemination of information easily ($\bar{x} = 3.02$), and Zoom technology makes my academic works easy and faster ($\bar{x} = 2.83$). Meanwhile, based on the value of the weighted average (2.88 out of 4.00 maximum value obtainable) which falls, within the decision value for **high**, it can be inferred that the perceived ease of use of Zoom Technology for teaching and learning among undergraduates' students in Adeyemi Federal University of Education (AFUED) is high.

Research Question 3:

What is the mean response of the respondents on the challenges while using zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?

Challenges Undergraduate Faced in Using Zoom Technology for Teaching and Learning

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D	Remark
Poor internet services by network providers (available but slow)	127	110	69	54	2.86	1.06	Accepted
High cost of internet facilities	219	89	28	24	3.39	.89	Accepted
Power outages	190	81	47	42	3.16	1.05	Accepted
High cost of internet access (subscription)	183	105	41	31	3.22	.96	Accepted
Lack of knowledge of how to use mobile zoom app effectively	242	104	14	0	3.63	.56	Accepted
Infrequent internet services (rarely available)	161	99	63	37	3.07	1.02	Accepted
Limited capacity to accommodate more participants during zoom meeting	95	104	151	10	2.79	.87	Accepted
Lack of devices for online learning such as smart phones, computers, tablets and smart TV	156	82	45	77	2.88	1.18	Accepted
High cost of devices for online learning such as smart phone, television and computer system.	176	109	30	45	3.16	1.03	Accepted
Insecurity problem (secret IDs provided to join the meeting can be predicted effortlessly)	134	92	86	48	2.87	1.06	Accepted

Key; *SD* = Strongly Disagree, *D* = Disagree, *A* = Agree, *SA* = Strongly Agree

Decision Value for Remark: *Not Accepted* = 0.00-2.44, *Accepted* = 2.45-4.00

Table 3 shows the challenges faced by the undergraduates while using the zoom technology for learning in AFUED. The table shows that the students agreed to all the items as follows: poor internet services by network providers (available but slow) (\bar{x} = 2.86), high cost of internet facilities (\bar{x} = 3.39), power outages (\bar{x} = 3.16), high cost of internet access (subscription) (\bar{x} = 3.22), lack of knowledge of how to use mobile zoom app effectively (\bar{x} = 3.63), infrequent internet services (rarely available) (\bar{x} = 3.07), limited capacity to accommodate more participants during zoom meeting (\bar{x} = 2.79), lack of devices for online learning such as smart phones, computers, tablets and smart TV (\bar{x} = 2.88), high cost of devices for online learning such as smart phone, television and computer system (\bar{x} = 3.16), and Insecurity problem (secret IDs provided to join the meeting can be predicted effortlessly (\bar{x} = 2.87). Based on the result from this table and mean score acceptance by the decision rule, it can be concluded that the challenges faced in using Zoom Technology for teaching and learning among undergraduate students in Adeyemi Federal University of Education (AFUED) are: poor internet services by network providers (available but slow), high cost of internet facilities, power outages, high cost of internet access (subscription), lack of knowledge of how to use mobile zoom app effectively, infrequent internet services (rarely available), limited capacity to accommodate more participants during zoom meeting, lack of devices for online learning such as smart phones, computers, tablets and smart TV, high cost of devices for online learning such as smart phone, television and computer system, and Insecurity problem (secret IDs provided to join the meeting can be predicted effortlessly).

Discussion of Results

From the research question one, the results shows that undergraduate students' level of use of zoom technology for learning in AFUED was low. This is evident as almost all the respondents disagreed that they use zoom in sharing information in educational blogs via cloud meetings, use Zoom cloud meetings to facilitate communication with many people, use zoom to read, view or listen to online academic programmes through cell-phones and other Internet facilities, use zoom to attempt online

assignments with instructions and guides from learning platforms, use zoom technology to improve their interaction with others on their academic works and use zoom technology to have access to learning anywhere and anytime. This finding is against the claim of Guzacheva (2020) who find out high level of utilization of zoom technology among students and teachers of English language in medical school.

From the research question two, the results show that undergraduate students' perceived ease of use of zoom technology was high. Majority of the students disagreed that they do not have confidence to use zoom technologies and believe that zoom technologies are too cumbersome for them to use. They also agreed that to the following; they feel interaction with zoom technologies will be very beneficial, feel it is easy to use zoom technologies, believe they have the necessary skills to use zoom technologies, it is easy to become skillful, if zoom technology is fully integrated, the use of zoom for instruction would enable them cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease, Zoom web application is user friendly to them and Zoom technology makes my academic works easy and faster. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Meladina & Zaswita (2020) who in their investigation find high ease of utilization of web-based learning tools among students in tertiary institutions.

From research question three, the result shows that there were challenges faced by undergraduate students in using zoom technology effectively in AFUED. This is evident as almost all the respondents agreed that they have the following challenges; poor internet services by network providers (available but slow), high cost of internet facilities, power outages, high cost of internet access (subscription), lack of knowledge of how to use mobile zoom app effectively, infrequent internet services (rarely available), limited capacity to accommodate more participants during zoom meeting and high cost of devices for online learning such as smart phone, television and computer system. This finding is in line with the findings of Franklin Ohiole & Nancwat Manna (2022) who in their investigation discovered lot of challenges affecting effective use of zoom for instruction in Ambrose Alli university Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study investigated the use of zoom technology for teaching and learning among undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria. The study also examined level and ease of use of zoom technology among undergraduate students for learning. It further examined some challenges hindering undergraduate students from effectively use zoom technology for learning. The findings revealed that the level of use of zoom by the undergraduate students was very low. While the perceived ease of zoom technology among undergraduate students was very high. The study further revealed that there were a lot of challenges confronting undergraduate students from effectively use zoom technology in AFUED.

The study also concluded that use of zoom technology for learning has emerged as a useful source for promoting learning and preparing youths to participate in a global economy. The important point that must be considered is the continuity of the video conference at this zoom depends on the internet network so that lecturers and students must use good and supportive internet access in order to use the zoom application for taking part in learning activities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the review of relevant literatures, the following recommendations were made:

1. University managements should intensify ICT training for students in order to equip them with the necessary skills and exposures to a range of co-curricular practical tasks on zoom technologies to help students become more encouraged and motivated to use zoom for learning.
2. The Universities should provide adequate, reliable zoom technology learning platform or software and tools to interconnect all students' and lecturers' for zoom technology learning.
3. The University authority should provide enabling environment that is free of challenges confronting undergraduate students from effectively use of zoom technology for learning.

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